

LEARNING ENGLISH THROUGH SOCIAL MEDIA

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10862945>

Annotation: The extensive and unique language material provided by the Internet can significantly speed up the process of learning a language. The global nature of the information changes taking place today is obvious, as is the need to revise approaches to education in general. The modern development of science, its liberation from stereotypes and innovative orientation requires the creative integration of modern approaches in the higher education system.

Informatization of the education system as a whole is the process of providing the education sector with the theory and practice of developing and using new information technologies focused on the implementation of psychological and pedagogical learning goals, which is one of the most important directions in the process of informatization of the educational space of modern society

In this article, the author shows the possibility of using social networks for teaching foreign languages.

Keywords: social networks, training, foreign languages.

A social network is an Internet platform, website, technology that allows you to post information about yourself, find information about other people, communicate with each other, establish new social connections or maintain existing ones. A social network is also a platform for transmitting various information between people.

Now it has become easy to find a group of interests online: educational, creative, technical. Today, society actively uses social networks to exchange information, communicate, work, and study. The use of various social networks has become part of the daily life of millions of people. The Internet makes it possible to communicate "here and now." This became a relevant method of interaction this year when the world faced an unexpected problem - a pandemic, when all work, study, shopping and entertainment moved online. Distance learning has made it possible to seriously consider social networks, not only as entertainment platforms for communicating, watching music or films, but also as

an educational platform that has helped ensure constant online work for teachers and students.¹

The main type of activity on the Internet is communication between people, reading any information, transferring data from one person to another. In social networks, communication occurs through language, so we can say that teaching a foreign language using web technologies will better develop the student's communicative competence. Language is a living system that is constantly changing. "The development of language, continuous and spontaneous, not amenable to control and planning, mysterious and uneven, constantly changes the distribution of semiotic connections in the language.

New functional relationships are superimposed on the old ones, coexist with them or gradually eliminate them". At this stage of human life, the main factor that changes language is the Internet and communication on social networks. Since the beginning of the active use of social networks, many new words have appeared that have entered our active vocabulary: hashtag, account, google, ban, content, click and many others. If we talk about foreign languages, then some words in them even changed their meaning, for example: "Friended", "friend" - in the usual sense these words mean "friendship, to be friends", but in the context of social media they acquired a new meaning - to add someone then to your "Friends" list on social networks. Just because you "friended" someone doesn't mean you have a real social connection. "Like" - the verb "to like" in a regular dictionary, which we can buy in any bookstore, means "to like," but if we are talking about the Internet, then "Like" has come to mean the degree of popularity of a person. "Smileys" or abbreviations, such as LOL (laughoutloud), OMG (OhmyGod), TTYL (talktoyoulater) , also began to play a big role. Since language is constantly changing, the relevance of using social networks for teaching a foreign language has increased dramatically. Modern language can now be heard on TV, radio, seen in newspapers and magazines, but most importantly on the Internet. For teenagers, it plays a big role what language their favorite blogger uses, what phrases their favorite characters use in a TV series or movie, than what can be found in a textbook. The textbook is the main basis for learning a language at school, but sometimes it becomes insufficient.

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- ¹ Gorbunova, Lyudmila Ivanovna. Language as a special kind of sign system: textbook / L. I. Gorbunova; Ministry of Education and Science of the Russian Federation, Federal State. budgetary educational institution of higher education prof. education "Irkutsk State. Univ., Fak. philology and journalism. - Irkutsk: ISU Publishing House, 2013. - 108 p.

Therefore, we can turn to various social networks.

Besides the fact that on social networks we can find authentic materials with relevant language for learning foreign languages, with the help of the Internet we can teach languages. Teaching foreign languages using the Internet is actively used by many teachers; there are many special platforms where children can learn foreign languages. But if we look at which Internet sites children use most often in real life, we will see their activity on the most popular social networks, such as Instagram, VK, twitter, YouTube and many others. These sites can be adapted for educational purposes.

Today we cannot do without social networks; we can talk a lot about their negative impact on people, but we should not perceive various popular Internet platforms only from the bad side. The use of social networks for learning foreign languages helps the teacher to attract attention to the lesson, to tasks, and allows the use of relevant language, which students must not only learn, but show by example how to apply it. Various Internet resources have penetrated into all spheres of society, especially in education, and their use is limited only by the teacher's imagination.

Literature:

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